
Towards a Mobile-based ADAS Simulation Framework

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Faculdade de Engenharia
FEUP

Agenda

1. Background

- 1.1. ADAS
- 1.2. Mobile-based ADAS
- 1.3. Distributed Mobile-based ADAS

2. Proposal

- 2.1. GeoStream
- 2.2. Driving Simulators
- 2.3. SUMO
- 2.4. Mobile-based ADAS

3. Preliminary verification

4. Conclusions & Future Work

1.1 Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS)

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- Navigation Systems (GPS)
 - Adaptive cruise control
 - Blind spot detection
 - Traffic sign recognition
 - Intelligent speed adaptation
 - Automatic parking
 - Lane departure warning system
 - Collision avoidance system
 - Driver drowsiness detection
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1.2 Mobile-based ADAS

- Huge number of mobile devices (increasing)
- A lot of unexplored helpful applications
- Easy and cheap setup
- Higher penetration

Fig. 1: Mobile-based ADAS

1.2 Testing Mobile-based ADAS

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- How to test them safely and in a low-cost environment?
 - Most simulation systems are complex or expensive!
(Driving simulators)
-

1.3 Distributed Mobile-based ADAS

- Seen as a single ADAS by the user
- Send feedback to the network (requires connectivity)
- Improve the overall reliability of the ADAS

Fig. 2: Distributed ADAS (Waze)

1.3 Testing Distributed Mobile-based ADAS

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How to test them?

(ADAS problems)ⁿ :(

2. Proposal

- SUMO, IC-DEEP ext.,
High Fidelity Simulators
- MAS
- Human Factors Analysis
- Open/processable data

Fig. 3: Proposal's architecture

2.1 GeoStream (OSM Import)

- Create environments that resemble reality
- Seamless import from OSM to Driving Simulators
- However SUMO network import is more complex (JOSM? Proprietary-Open GIS?)

Fig. 4: Data import to Unity3D engine

2.2 Driving Simulators

- DRIS High-Fidelity Simulator
- IC-DEEP low cost simulator (Unity3D Serious game)
- Share the simulation state

Fig. 5: DRIS @ FEUP

Fig. 6: IC-DEEP @ LIACC

2.3 SUMO

Coupling (Work in Progress)

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Requirements

- Synchronize simulation state
- Coherent simulation representation
- Human-in-the-loop simulation
- Include ADAS testing capabilities

Challenges

- Allow latitudinal movement (lane “freedom”)
 - Possible communication bottleneck?
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2.4 Mobile-based ADAS (GPS Mocking)

- Bound service receives socket communications
- Changes the device status
- Noticeable by all running applications (even Google Navigation)

Fig. 7: Mobile ADAS architecture

3.1 Preliminary verification (GeoStream & IC-DEEP)

- Real GPS logging driving at Porto's downtown.
- Cross-validate results in our simulator with Google Earth
- Reproduce the circuit in the simulator

Fig. 8: GPS logs analysis

3.2 Preliminary verification (ADAS testing)

- Driving statistics meet those of the driving simulator (speed and distance)
- Successful coupling and usage of other system apps (Google Navigation)

Fig. 9: Developed test ADAS

4.1 Testing Mobile-based ADAS

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- How to test them safely and in a low-cost environment?
- Most simulation systems are complex or expensive!
(Driving simulators)

4.1 Testing Mobile-based ADAS

- How to test them safely and in a low-cost environment?
- Most simulation systems are complex or expensive!
(Driving simulators)

Extend IC-DEEP with ADAS testing capabilities

4.2 Testing Distributed Mobile-based ADAS

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How to test them?

(ADAS problems)ⁿ :(

4.2 Testing Distributed Mobile-based ADAS

How to test them?

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Mobile-based ADAS Simulation Framework
(SUMO + IC-DEEP extension + MAS)

4.3 Conclusions

- Successfully tested Mobile-based ADAS
 - Testing Distributed Mobile-based ADAS is a challenge
 - Requires more integration & synchronization
 - Communication bottleneck with micro-simulators
 - Coupling different simulators is desirable...
 - ... to allow multifaceted simulations
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4.4 Future Work

- SUMO coupling with IC-DEEP
 - DRIS (High-Fidelity) Simulator integration
 - Include behaviour elicitation through peer-designed agents
 - Use the latter to implement a MAS and model cultural/geographical idiosyncrasies
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ADAS Interaction

Serious Games

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*“A mental contest, **played with a computer in accordance with specific rules, that uses entertainment to further government or corporate training, education, health, public policy, and strategic communication objectives.**”*

- Michael Zyda

Serious Games - why?

- Conducting Human Factor Analysis
- Simulate Artificial Societies with behaviour elicitation through peer-designed agents

Fig. 10: IC-DEEP @ LIACC

Interesting questions...

- How does SUMO connect to multiple mobile devices?
 - How much data preparation is needed for SUMO?
 - Why Distributed ADAS pose a bottleneck in the simulation?
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